

CLINICAL STUDIES ON SEASONAL INFLUENCE OF ATMOSPHERIC CHANGES ON ARTERIAL BLOOD PRESSURE AND EFFECT OF AN AYURVEDIC COMPOUND DRUG ON IT

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension is a disease of gradual, insidious onset with no specific features to start with, so its detection was not easy before the discovery of Stethoscope and Sphygmomanometer. Seasonal variation in arterial blood pressure has been reported in studies with hypertensive and normotensive subjects. A high blood pressure may vary by season, study shows higher doses of medication may be needed in winter; by Charlene Laino , Web MD Medical News, Nov. 5, 2007 (Orlando, Fla.). The findings suggest that people with high blood pressure may need higher doses of medication or even different drugs in the winter months, says researcher Ross D. Fletcher, MD, chief of staff at the VA Medical Center in Washington, D.C. As far as Ayurveda is concerned, it is supposed to be the oldest medical literature available in the world; but no any disease in the classics can exactly correlate with hypertension. The authors hold the view that the disorders which are tends to persist round the year must have some seasonal influence over there causation and severity; like wise hypertension is a disorder of pressure homeostasis, that can be easily influenced by atmospheric pressure and temperature changes. A clinical study has been performed to assess the effect of an Ayurvedic compound drug on it with an aim to evaluate the effect of season on its severity.

Key words- Hypertension, seasonal variation, Ayurveda, Vata vyadhi

Introduction

Seasonal variation in arterial blood pressure has been reported in studies with hypertensive and normotensive subjects. The Medical Research Council of England studied seasonal variation of blood pressure in 17,000 treated or untreated hypertensive patients and observed

that blood pressure increases by approximately 7/3 mm Hg in the winter compared to the summer. Both doctors and patients are aware of the effects of changes in temperature on blood pressure. Patients in the borderline-to-mild hypertensive range often need pharmacologic treatment only in winter, and hypertensive patients themselves may spontaneously decrease their medications during summer. Despite the published evidence of the clinical influence of temperature changes on risk factors like hypertension, this phenomenon is often overlooked. Moreover, the prevalence of strokes and myocardial infarction was found to increase in winter. In north India, the proportion of patients with hypertension (with and without coronary artery disease) was the greatest in winter and declined during summer.

The causes of seasonal variation in blood pressure are not clear, although some studies have reported an inverse correlation between blood pressure and environmental temperature. A high blood pressure may vary by season, study shows higher doses of medication may be needed in winter; by Charlene Laino , Web MD Medical News, reviewed by Louise Chang, MD, Nov. 5, 2007 (Orlando, Fla.). The findings suggest that people with high blood pressure may need higher doses of medication or even different drugs in the winter months, says researcher Ross D. Fletcher, MD, chief of staff at the VA Medical Center in Washington, D.C. The author holds the view that the disorders which are tends to persist round the year must have some seasonal influence of Dosha over their causation and severity; similarly, the treatment scenario of them should be different in summer than the winter season; like wise hypertension is a disorder of pressure homeostasis, that can be easily influenced by atmospheric pressure and temperature changes.

There is no any disease found in the Ayurvedic literature, which correlate exactly with hypertension, but on the basis of involved Dosha, Dushya, Adhithana and Lakshana it is sure to say that it is a Vata vyadhi especially Avritta Vata vyadhi; because like Vata vyadhi, hypertension is initially symptom less (Avyakta lakshama) and lately manifests fleetingly (Apay and laghuta). (Cha.Chi-28/19)

The whole year is divided in to six parts according to seasons. The northward movement of the sun and its act of dehydration (Adana kala) bring about three seasons beginning from late winter to summer. The southward movement of the sun and its act of hydration (Visarga kala) give rise to other three seasons beginning with the rainy to early winters (Ch.Su-6/4). Adana kala is dominated by Sun, have weakened the strength, the air becomes dry and ranges from mid of January to mid of July; while Visarga kala is dominated

by Moon, gives the strength, air is not dry and is assorted from mid of July to mid of January. According to proposed hypothesis there must be some influence of a season on the Doshik status of the patients of the hypertension, which is well supported by modern geological researches. Ayurveda advocates the tricky use of Ayurvedic drugs on the basis of there Rasa, Guna, Virya, and Vipaka differently in different seasons was the basis for this study.

Material and Methods-

Aims and Objectives of the clinical study

- Effect of atmospheric pressure on arterial blood pressure in hypertensive patients has been assessed
- An Ayurvedic compound drug has been designed for lowering the BP over the basis of its pathogenesis and symptomatology; and the effect was analyzed statistically.

Selection of the Patients-

In the present clinical work, a series of 50 patients age between 40 to 70 years of uncomplicated mild to moderate essential hypertension were undergone study. They were randomly selected from the OPD and IPD of Panchakarma, Sir Sunder Lal Hospital, Institute of Medical Sciences, BHU, Varanasi; during the year 15th February 2024 to 14th February 2025.

Exclusion criteria-

The patients, who had raised arterial blood pressure associated with the following condition, were excluded from the study. Patients with severe/malignant hypertension, Secondary hypertension, Mild/moderate hypertension with complications or target organ damage.

Diagnostic criteria-

Diagnosis of hypertension is mainly objective, which is based on elevated level of sphygmomanometric reading. Initially to have a diagnosis, 2 sets of readings separated by 20 to 30 minutes interval were taken; repeated same procedure after one week of physical and mental rest. When systolic and diastolic BP falls into different categories, the higher category had been selected to classify the individual BP status. We categorize the patient on the basis of "VII Joint National Committee criteria on detection, evaluation and treatment of high blood pressure (1998) report as shown below:

Sl. No.	Category	Systolic B.P.	Diastolic BP
1.	Normal	<130 mmHg	<85 mmHg
2.	High normal	130-139 mmHg	85-89 mmHg

	Hypertension		
3.	Stage I (mild)	140-159 mmHg	90-99 mmHg
4.	Stage II (Moderate)	160-179 mmHg	100-109 mmHg
5.	Stage III (Severe)	180-210 mmHg	110-119 mmHg
6.	Stage IV (very severe)	> 210 mmHg	>120 mmHg

Investigations-

No any specific investigation is claimed to be associated with the diagnosis of essential hypertension; but to rule out any concomitant disease and/or secondary or malignant or complicated hypertension, routine investigations has been performed like Hb%, blood Urea, blood sugar (Fasting), serum creatinine and ECG.

Preparation of the Trial drug-

The drugs were designed in such a way that it could stop the pathogenesis of hypertension along with suppression of raised arterial blood pressure and resulted into clinical improvement. The comparative studies of all the drugs used in the trial are shown in the following table. Initially the coarse powder (yavkuta) of whole drug was decocted (Sa.sa.-2/1-2) and converted into there Ghana (semi solid) form except of Vatsanabha, which is first processed to detoxify with the treatment of Cow urine and steaming in Dola yantra; lately purified Vatsanabha powder is added in required quantity, mixed well and converted in to pills of approximately 750 mg. weight.

Trial Ayurvedic Compound drug (TD)							
Name	Bo. Name	Group / Property	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Dose
Aendri	Bacopa.-monneri	Medhya Anti stress	Tikta	Laghu	Ushna	Katu	2 gm/day
Sarpagandha	Rauwolfia-serpentina	Nidrakar Hypnotic	Tikta	Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	1 gm/day
Punarnava	Boerhavia.-diffusa	Mutrala Diuretic	Madhur Tikta	Laghu Ruksha	Ushna	Madhur	3 gm/day
Vatsanabha	Aconitum-ferox	Swedjanan Sweat producing	Madhur	Ruksha Tikshna Vyvayi Vikasi	Ushna	Madhur	15 mg/day.

Administration of Drugs and Follow up study-

Total 50 patients had been taken for trial and divided into two groups:

Group TDA (Trial drug during Adana kala)

In this group 25 patients of both sexes had been taken for clinical assessment of Trial drug 'TD', they were registered and kept on for follow up study strictly during the Adana kala i.e. from 15th February to 14th August, had been advised 2 pills (1.5 gm.) two times a day (3 gm/day) orally for two months, with a fifteen days follow up, but only 20 patients were turned up for complete follow up.

Group TDV (Trial drug during Visarga kala)

In this group 25 patients of both sexes had been taken for clinical assessment of Trial drug 'TD', they were registered and kept on for follow up study strictly during the Visarga kala i.e. from 15th August to 14th February, they were advised 2 pills (1.5 gm.) two times a day (3 gm/day) orally for two months, with a fifteen days follow up, in this group all the 25 patients were turned up for complete follow up.

Assessment of Results-

The results of the treatment were assessed as excellent, good, fair and poor at the end of two months of drug therapy; the parameters of the assessment were taken as follows:

1. Excellent: when the fall in DBP is found ≥ 16 mm Hg, and SBP ≥ 31 mmHg.
2. Good: when the fall in DBP is found 11-15 mmHg, and SBP 21-30 mmHg.
3. Fair: when the fall in DBP is 6-10 mmHg, and SBP 11-20 mmHg.
4. Poor: when the fall in DBP is 0-5 mmHg; and SBP 0-10mmHg.

Statistical analysis-

Systolic Blood Pressure & Diastolic Blood Pressure were calculated and statistically analyzed by Mean, SD, SE, 't' values and 'P' values. The degree of significance was calculated by comparing the effect of therapy with there own initial BP readings, as well as with the other group.

Observation-

The geographical position of Varanasi and its adjacent 10 districts are classified as buffer zone where Himalayan range is near to end and Vindhya range is going to start. So, the annual calendar is prepared according to Vindhyan zone where rainy season is more prolonged than winters, hence Pravrita ritu is included in the calendar where as the Shishira ritu is not there. (Su.Su- 6/10)

- Longitude - 83⁰ 01 minute
- Latitude - 25⁰ 18 minute
- Altitude – 76 meter above mean sea level
- Annual rain fall – 1076 mm./year
- Mean annual surface pressure – 998.4 hpa
- Mean annual temperature – 32.1 max./19.2 min.
- Mean annual humidity – 70 (8:30 AM) /55 (5:30 PM)

Table no-1; Atmospheric variability of pressure, temperature & humidity month wise in Varanasi geographical area

Month	Atmospheric Pressure (hpa)	Atmospheric Temp. max (°C)	Atmospheric Temp. min (°C)	Mean atmospheric Pre. Temp. & Hum.	Humidity Morning 8:30 am	Humidity Evening 5:30 pm	
January	1007.2	23.0	9.0	993.25 hpa 36.1/23.4°C 63.17/47.33	84	60	
February	1004.6	26.3	11.6		72	47	
March	1001.1	32.5	16.3		(Summer months)	53	32
April	996.5	38.5	21.6			41	23
May	992.8	44.4	25.5			49	28
June	988.8	40.5	26.9			69	49
July	989.2	33.7	25.5		82	75	
August	991.1	33	24.6		85	77	
September	995.3	32.6	24.4		(Winter months)	84	74
October	1001.3	32.6	20.3			75	66
November	1005.0	29.4	14.4			73	62
December	1007.7	24.6	9.6			1003.52 hpa 28.0/14.89°C 78.16/62.17	81

Table no-2; Assessment of improvement in systolic blood pressure (SBP)

Group	Initial	F1	F2	F3	F4	Difference Initial vs. F4
TDA (N=20)	154.22±7.09	150.15±6.31	146.90±6.37	143.15±6.66	140.10±6.34	13.60±5.09 t=11.94 p<0.001 HS
TDV (N=25)	160.16±10.28	151.52±10.85	146.32±8.97	141.88±7.54	136.56±6.84	23.60±9.04 t=12.56 p<0.001 HS

Table no-3; Assessment of improvement in diastolic blood pressure (DBP)

Group	Initial	F1	F2	F3	F4	Difference Initial vs. F4
TDA (N=20)	98.16±3.94	96.25±3.84	93.40±3.50	91.60±4.19	89.10±3.92	9.00±3.34 t=12.05 p<0.001 HS
TDV (N=25)	101.20±3.73	96.08±6.96	93.44±6.34	90.24±6.51	86.80±5.51	14.40±4.44 t=16.20 p<0.001 HS

N = number of patients, FU = Follow Up, HS = highly significant, BT = before treatment, AT = after treatment

Table no-4; Inter group comparison of improvement in (SBP) & (DBP)

<u>TDA vs. TDV for SBP</u>	<u>TDA vs. TDV for DBP</u>
t =4.28 p<0.001 HS	t =4.51 p<0.001 HS
Group-TDA (N=20) Mean SBP (BT)-154.32±7.09	Group-TDV (N=25) Mean SBP (BT)-160.16±10.28

Mean SBP (AT)-140.10±6.34	Mean SBP (AT)-136.56±6.84
Mean DBP (BT)- 98.16±3.94	Mean DBP (BT)- 101.20±3.73
Mean DBP(AT)- 89.10±3.92	Mean DBP(AT)- 86.80±5.51
Effect- Excellent- 1 Good- 5	Effect- Excellent- 13 Good- 9
Fair- 13 Poor- 1	Fair- 3 Poor- 0

Discussion-

It is very well understood by observing the table no.-1, that atmospheric pressure is higher in the winter months (Visarga kala) where as low in the summer months (Adana kala); the cause for the low atmospheric pressure in the summer months can be the higher level of atmospheric temperature during these days. Because it is proved that when the temperature of the surface level gases goes high it takes the wind to upper strata and leads to low pressure in the surface area. This low surface pressure during summer months probably influences the human body to accommodate on lower level of blood pressure. The things will be opposite in the winter months. On comparison of mean atmospheric pressure during summer months (from March to August, readings in bold letter, 993.25hpa) and winter months (from September to February, readings in italic letter, 1003.52hpa) it is evident that atmospheric pressure varies in a wide range. There is approximately 10 hpa difference of pressure in between these two-time period zone. The temperature difference was found approximately 8⁰C between the mean of highest and lowest monthly temperature of summer and winter months. The atmospheric pressure was 10 hpa lower in the summer months while the mean temperature was 8⁰C higher in these months. So it is confirmed that as the atmospheric temperature rises the atmospheric pressure goes down at surface level. On the other hand atmospheric humidity was largest in the rainy season, but on comparison of mean value it is observed that humidity in winter season was 15% greater than that of summer season; so it can be assumed that it is a Kapha kala, while mean temperature was 8⁰C higher in summer month than winter period; so it can be understood as Pitta kala. Further the mean SBP during summer months was found to be 154.22±7.09, whereas in winter months it was 160.16±10.28; a difference of nearly 6 mmHg was observed. The mean DBP during summer months was 98.16±3.94 and during winter months 101.20±3.73; which again shows a difference of around 3 mmHg.

On observing table no.-2; In group TDA (Compound drug treated group during summer months), the initial mean SBP was 154.22±7.09 mmHg, after treatment with

compound drug the mean SBP was reduced to 150.15 ± 6.31 , 146.90 ± 6.37 , 143.15 ± 6.66 and 140.10 ± 6.34 mmHg respectively on 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th follow up. The difference between initial verses 4th follow up was 13.60 ± 5.09 , the t was 11.94 and $p < 0.001$; which was found highly significant. Whereas in group TDV (Trial drug treated group during winter months), the initial mean SBP was 160.16 ± 10.28 mmHg, after treatment with compound drug the mean SBP was reduced to 151.52 ± 10.85 , 146.32 ± 8.97 , 141.88 ± 7.54 and 136.56 ± 6.84 mmHg respectively on 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th follow up. The difference between initial verses 4th follow up was 23.60 ± 9.04 , the t was 12.56 and $p < 0.001$; which was also found highly significant.

On examining the table no.-3, it is evident that in group TDA (Trial drug treated group during summer months), the initial mean DBP was 98.16 ± 3.94 mmHg, after treatment with compound drug the mean DBP was reduced to 96.25 ± 3.84 , 93.40 ± 3.50 , 91.60 ± 4.19 and 89.10 ± 3.92 mmHg respectively on 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th follow up. The difference between initial verses 4th follow up was 9.00 ± 3.34 , the t was 12.05 and $p < 0.001$; which was found highly significant. Whereas in group BV (Compound drug treated group during winter months), the initial mean DBP was 101.20 ± 3.73 mmHg, after treatment with compound drug the mean DBP was reduced to 96.08 ± 6.96 , 93.44 ± 6.34 , 90.24 ± 6.51 and 86.80 ± 5.51 mmHg respectively on 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th follow up. The difference between initial verses 4th follow up was 14.40 ± 4.44 , the t was 16.20 and $p < 0.001$; which was also found highly significant.

Table no.-4 expresses the comparison of effect between the two groups. The post therapeutic difference of SBP and DBP between the two time periods with the same drug was found highly significant. This indicates that the effect of compound drug in lowering SBP and DBP over the patients of hypertension during winter months (group TDV) was more in comparison to summer months (group TDA). More so because all the drugs used here for the treatment were having Ushna and Katu properties which were also beneficial for Kapha dosha; normally aggravates during winter season (Visarga kala). The over all improvement in terms of excellent, good, fair and poor response the results were found in favor of compound drug used in winter months then summer months. In group TDA the excellent response was found in 1 patient, good response was observed in 5 patients whereas 13 patients have shown fair response and 1 patient have reported poor response to the treatment. In group TDV the results were really amazing with the same drug the excellent response was found in 13 patients, good response was observed in 9 patients whereas 3 patients have shown fair response but no any patient have been reported under poor response category.

Conclusion

The following conclusions have been drawn, Varanasi and its adjacent 10 districts are classified as under eastern Vindhyan zone, so the annual calendar prepared has been according to Vindhya area, where rainy period is more prolonged than the winter period; hence Pravrita is included in the calendar whereas Shishira is omitted. The whole outer universe is governed by pressure, temperature and humidity changes, while the inner universe is governed by Vata, Pitta and Kapha changes, both are conceptually similar. Elevation of atmospheric temperature decreases the arterial blood pressure level. Seasonal variation has shown strong influence over the arterial blood pressure with in 7/3 mmHg of SBP and DBP level respectively. Successful reduction of arterial blood pressure has been observed with the treatment of compound Ayurvedic drug. The decrease of SBP and DBP was reported more in winter months than in summer months; supports the hypothesis that doshik influence has also plays a powerful role in causation and severity of hypertension. Symptomatically all of the registered cases had shown excellent response to the compound drug treatment. Hence it can be said that compound drug is a reliable remedy for treating hypertension from Ayurvedic point of view.

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